

Started on	Thursday, 21 September 2023, 1:07 PM
State	Finished
Completed on	Wednesday, 4 October 2023, 3:40 PM
Time taken	13 days 2 hours
Overdue	13 days 1 hour

Question 1

Not answered

Not graded

Consent of research participant

I have been asked to participate in the DigiTala research project funded by the Academy of Finland. The data will be pseudonymized and used in the DigiTala and [Kielibuusti - Språkboost](#) projects as well as stored in [the Language Bank](#) for legitimate research purposes only.

I have received sufficient information about the research and its purpose, the content and use of the material, including the processing and storage of personal data. By filling this form, I confirm that I have received the [information sheet for research participants](#) and privacy notice (helsinki.fi/en/digitala/privacy)

I understand that participation in this research is voluntary. I have the right to discontinue participation in the research at any time. I am not required to state the reason for the withdrawal and there will be no negative consequences.

Select one:

- a. Yes, I do give my consent.
- b. No, I do not.

Question 2

Not answered

Not graded

Please answer the following background questions:

Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Age:

- 15-21
- 22-26
- 27-60
- 61+

Mother Tongue:

- Arabic
- English
- Finnish
- Kurdish
- Russian
- Somali
- Swedish
- Other

Other, please specify:**Other language skills:****Question 3**

Not answered

Not graded

Mic test

- Click on "Start recording" > Say: "**testing, testing**" > Click on) "Stop recording".
- Click on "play" > Do you hear your voice? > Start the test!
- Can't hear your voice?
 - Enable your mic on browser). See for help: [screenshot 1](#) and [screenshot 2](#).
 - Click on the mic or camera symbol > Click on "allow" and "remember this decision"
 - Ask DigiTala team members for help

No recording

Question 4

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1a) Read aloud

Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the word below:

Banan

Source: <https://pixabay.com/fi/illustrations/banaani-hedelmi%c3%a4-keltainen-makea-2850841/>

No recording

Question 5

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1b) Read aloud

Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the word below:

Puss

Source: <https://pixabay.com/fi/illustrations/suudella-huulet-suun-2931833/>

No recording

Question 6

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1c) Read aloud

Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the word below:

Dyr

Source: <https://pixabay.com/fi/vectors/raha-kolikko-k%c3%a4teinen-raha-1673582/>

No recording

Question 7

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1d) Read aloud

Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the word below:

Kanske

Source: <https://pixabay.com/fi/vectors/ajattelija-ajattelu-henkil%c3%b6-idea-28741/>

No recording

Question 8

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1e) Read aloud*Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the sentence:***Jag tycker om att sjunga.**Source: <https://pixabay.com/images/id-1295782/>

No recording

Question 9

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1f) Read aloud*Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the sentence:***Han kommer från Kina.**

Image: Papunetin kuvapankki, papunet.net, Paxtoncrafts Charitable Trust

No recording

Question 10

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1g) Read aloud*Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the sentence:***Vill du äta här?**

Image: Papunetin kuvapankki, papunet.net, Elina Vanninen

No recording

Question 11

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 1h) Read aloud*Click on "Start recording" and read aloud the sentence:***På kvällen är jag på gymmet.**

Image: Papunetin kuvapankki, papunet.net, Kuvako

No recording

Question 12

Not answered

Marked out of 3.00

Task 2) My day

Tell about your day. Do not use real names or addresses. Click on "Start recording" and try to speak for 1 minute. Supporting questions:

- Vilken tid vaknar du?
- Vad äter du och dricker du på morgonen?
- Vad gör du på dagen?
- Vem träffar du?
- Var är du på kvällen?
- Vad gör du på kvällen?
- Vilken tid sover du?

No recording

Information**Task 3) What would you say?**

You meet your new classmate in a café. **What can you say in the following situations? Reply using full sentences.**

Question 13

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 3a) Click on "Start recording" and **order a coffee**

Image: Papunetin kuvapankki, papunet.net, Annakaisa Ojanen

No recording

Question 14

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 3b) Click on "Start recording" and **ask how much the coffee costs**

Image: Papunetin kuvapankki, papunet.net, Kuvako

No recording

Question 15

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 3c) Click on "Start recording" and **answer to your friend who calls and asks where you are.**

Image: Papunetin kuvapankki, papunet.net, Paxtoncrafts Charitable Trust

No recording

Question 16

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 3d) Click on "Start recording" and **ask your friend at least two questions. You want to get to know him/her.**

Image: Papunetin kuvapankki, papunet.net, Sclera, muokkaus Heidi Ahlström

No recording

Question 17

Not answered

Marked out of 4.00

Task 4) Tell about the picture

Tell about the picture. What do you see? Try to speak for 1 minute. Plan for a moment what you are going to say. Then click on "Start recording".

Supporting questions:

- Hurdan är familjen? (medlemmar, hur gamla)
- Vad gör de?
- Vad dricker de?
- Var är de?
- Var bor de?

Source: <https://pixabay.com/fi/vectors/perhe-vanhemmat-isovanhemmat-lapset-6351117/> (downloaded 16.12.2022)

No recording

Information**Task 5) Interviewing a classmate**

Your homework is to interview a classmate. You talk on the phone and get to know each other. **Listen to your classmate and answer the questions.** Do not give real addresses or names.

Question 18

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 5a) Lyssna på frågan och spela in ditt svar.

Listen to the question and record your answer.

[Audio: vad heter du?]

No recording

Question 19

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 5b) Lyssna på frågan och spela in ditt svar.

Listen to the question and record your answer.

Audio: varifrån kommer du?

No recording

Question 20

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 5c) Lyssna på frågan och spela in ditt svar.

Listen to the question and record your answer.

Audio: vilka språk talar du?

No recording

Question 21

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 5d) Lyssna på frågan och spela in ditt svar.

Listen to the question and record your answer.

Audio: var jobbar eller studerar du?

No recording

Question 22

Not answered

Marked out of 1.00

Task 5e) Lyssna på frågan och spela in ditt svar.

Listen to the question and record your answer.

Audio: hurdan familj har du?

No recording

Question 23

Not answered

Not graded

Please give feedback! You can write also in English.

1) What is your impression of the test?

- 1 Very positive 2 Positive 3 Not positive nor negative 4 Negative 5 Very negative

2) What do you think about the content of the test?

(1 = Completely disagree; 2 = Quite disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Quite agree; 5 = Completely agree)

A) The instructions were clear and I understood what I was expected to do in the test.

- 1 2 3 4 5

B) It was easy for me to understand the materials (texts, pictures, recordings) that appeared in the tasks.

- 1 2 3 4 5

C) The topics of the tasks interested me.

- 1 2 3 4 5

D) I learned something new.

- 1 2 3 4 5

E) The test tasks reminded everyday situations.

- 1 2 3 4 5

F) The exam tested the skills I have practiced during Swedish lessons.

- 1 2 3 4 5

G) The test was the right length for me.

- 1 2 3 4 5

H) The test tasks were of an appropriate level for me.

- 1 2 3 4 5

I) Completing these tasks gives a true picture of my oral language skills.

- 1 2 3 4 5

3) What do you think about the tasks?**4) Any technical problems?****5) Anything else worth mentioning?**